

DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACOLOGY AND PHYTOCHEMISTRY - SCIENCE'S OFFER FOR THE INDUSTRY AND AGRICULTURE.

Baraniak J., Kania - Dobrowolska M., Gryszczyńska A., Miklaś M., Opala B., Pietrowiak A., Łowicki Z., Ożarowski M, Mikołajczak P. Ł., Seremak - Mrozikiewicz A.

Institute of Natural Fibres and Medicinal Plants, Department of Pharmacology and Phytochemistry,
ul. Kolejowa 2, 62-064 Plewiska
e-mail of corresponding author: justyna.baraniak@iwnirz.pl

Department of Pharmacology and Phytochemistry offers wide spectrum of research activities and service for the pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic industry. Mainly, diet supplements and foods for particular nutritional uses projects and also safety assessment performed by our Department can lead to obtain a new innovative products. Additionally, all these innovative products can be detailed verify with the use of qualitative and quantitative analysis of active substances and phytochemical analysis of plant substances.

We are engaged in development of analytical methods and their validation, testing of raw materials of pharmaceutical and medicinal products for compliance with the requirements and specifications of European and Polish Pharmacopoeia.

We also offer our help in composition of products, appropriate products qualification and law requirements which are necessary to register food supplement.

We can also prepare scientific data concerning efficacy, safety and possible interactions of particular herbal substances or their preparations.

REFERENCES

Directive 2002/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 June 2002.

Rozporządzenie Ministra Zdrowia z dnia 23 marca 2011 r. w sprawie wzoru formularza powiadomienia o produktach wprowadzonych po raz pierwszy do obrotu na terytorium Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej, rejestru produktów objętych powiadomieniem oraz wykazu krajowych jednostek naukowych właściwych do wydawania opinii.

Ustawa z dnia 6 września 2001 r. Prawo farmaceutyczne. Dz.U. 2001 nr 126 poz. 1381.

